

Croissant - User Research Report

- **Title:** Croissant: A Metadata Format for ML-Ready Datasets
- **Links**
 - **Specification:** <https://docs.mlcommons.org/croissant/docs/croissant-spec.html>
 - **Working Group:** <https://mlcommons.org/working-groups/data/croissant/>
 - **More details:** <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3650203.3663326>
- **Author(s):** MLC Croissant WG
- **Last date of update:** August 14, 2024
- **Version:** 0.1

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Abstract

This document serves as a user research report for validating the metadata from automatically generated Croissant files. The validation is done for the selected datasets by human annotators based on the provided guidelines for verifying standard metadata attributes such as correctness, reproducibility, completeness, readability, etc. Although, we aim to do so but do not claim to gather insights on all of these attributes.

Annotation Instructions to the Users

Croissant Manual Evaluation

(Takes approx. 15 minutes to complete BUT as you start annotating, please note down the time as you will be asked afterwards how long it took to complete the annotations.)

Croissant is a metadata format that simplifies the integration and use of datasets across diverse machine learning frameworks such as PyTorch, TensorFlow, and JAX. It provides a structured vocabulary for dataset attributes, facilitating the seamless exchange and utilization of datasets, which addresses challenges in discoverability, portability, reproducibility, and responsible AI (RAI).

Thank you for participating in this manual evaluation of the Croissant format. Your expertise and insights are crucial to enhancing its effectiveness and usability across various platforms. As part of this evaluation, you will be assigned one dataset from the [HuggingFace datasets library](#). After accessing and reviewing the dataset, you will be asked to annotate it according to the 16 specified attributes listed in the instruction manual.

Your contributions are invaluable to us, and we appreciate your efforts in helping improve the Croissant metadata format for the wider machine learning community.

INSTRUCTIONS ANNOTATION PROCESS

1. First, look at the following attributes below to understand what information is requested from you about the dataset:

a. Croissant Core attributes to Evaluate:

1. sc:description - Description of the dataset.
2. sc:license - License details of the dataset, preferably a URL from a recognized source like SPDX.
3. sc:name - The official name of the dataset.
4. sc:url - URL where the dataset can be accessed.
5. sc:creator - The creator(s) of the dataset, which can be an organization or person.
6. sc:publisher - The publisher of the dataset, possibly distinct from the creator.
7. sc:datePublished - The publication date of the dataset.
8. sc:inLanguage - The language(s) in which the dataset content is available.
9. cr:citeAs - Recommended citation for the dataset.
10. cr:isLiveDataset - Indicator of whether the dataset is actively maintained and updated.

b. RAI attributes to evaluate:

11. rai:dataCollection - Description of the data collection process.
12. rai:dataCollectionTimeframe - Start and end date of the data collection process.
13. rai:dataAnnotationPlatform - Platform or tool used for data annotation.
14. rai:annotatorDemographics - Demographics of the annotators involved in the dataset labeling.
15. rai:dataUseCases - Potential uses of the dataset for AI safety and fairness evaluation.
16. rai:personalSensitiveInformation - Details about any personal sensitive information included in the dataset.

2. Second, if you need further details to understand the attributes check out the resources below:

- Croissant attributes documentation: <https://miccommons.github.io/croissant/docs/croissant-spec.html#dataset-level-information>
- Croissant responsible AI (RAI) attributes documentation: <https://miccommons.github.io/croissant/docs/croissant-rai-spec.html#rai-property-information>

3. Third, checkout the following dataset:

Dataset for Evaluation: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/cais/mmlu>

4. Search if a publication or Huggingface dataset card is available describing the dataset. If so, take a look at the publication and/or dataset card, focusing on the dataset description and its creation process.

Enter links to all external resources you used below:

5. Complete the JSON template below, describing all sixteen attributes for the dataset you find under (3.)

Please consider the following:

- To fill the attributes only use the dataset (see HuggingFace link above) and dataset documentations you find (e.g. a research paper or website describing the dataset)
- Do not use the Croissant metadata file of the dataset if one is available (e.g. on HuggingFace)
- If an attribute is not applicable to the dataset, enter **"NA"** as value.
- If an attribute is applicable but no information is provided in the dataset or paper, enter **"Unknown"**.

Fill all requested attributes in the JSON snippet below:

```
{
  // Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "",
  "sc:license": "",
  "sc:name": "",
  "sc:url": "",
  "sc:creator": "",
  "sc:publisher": "",
  "sc:datePublished": "",
  "sc:inLanguage": "",
  "cr:citeAs": "",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "",
  // RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": ""
}
```

6. Enter (contact) information below and answer the questions:

Individual Responses

This section describes the responses received from the annotators for different datasets. We have anonymised the responses to ensure privacy of the annotators.

Dataset 1 - LibriSpeech dataset

- **Overview of Dataset 1:**
 - Link - https://huggingface.co/datasets/librispeech_asr
- **Annotator 1:**

```
{
  // Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "LibriSpeech is a corpus of approximately 1000 hours of 16kHz read English speech, prepared by Vassil Panayotov with the assistance of Daniel Povey. The data is derived from read audiobooks from the LibriVox project, and has been carefully segmented and aligned.",
  "sc:license": "Creative Commons 4.0",
```

```

"sc:name": "librispeech_asr",
"sc:url": "https://huggingface.co/datasets/librispeech_asr",
"sc:creator": "Vassil Panayotov et al.",
"sc:publisher": "IEEE",
"sc:datePublished": "06 August 2015 ",
"sc:inLanguage": "English",
"cr:citeAs": "{ 'chapter_id': 141231,
'file':
'/home/patrick/.cache/huggingface/datasets/downloads/extracted/b7ded9969e09942a
b65313e691e6fc2e12066192ee8527e21d634aca128afbe2/dev_clean/1272/141231/1272-141
231-0000.flac',
'audio': { 'path':
'/home/patrick/.cache/huggingface/datasets/downloads/extracted/b7ded9969e09942a
b65313e691e6fc2e12066192ee8527e21d634aca128afbe2/dev_clean/1272/141231/1272-141
231-0000.flac',
'array': array([-0.00048828, -0.00018311, -0.00137329, ..., 0.00079346,
0.00091553, 0.00085449], dtype=float32),
'sampling_rate': 16000},
'id': '1272-141231-0000',
'speaker_id': 1272,
'text': 'A MAN SAID TO THE UNIVERSE SIR I EXIST'}",
"cr:isLiveDataset": "No",
// RAI attributes
"rai:dataCollection": "LibriVox's API with the
metadata records from the Internet Archive6 and Project Gutenberg's
RDF/XML files7.",
"rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "",
"rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "words are generated with the Sequitur G2P
toolkit; Voxforge",
"rai:annotatorDemographics": "volunteer",
"rai:dataUseCases": "training and evaluating speech recognition systems.",
"rai:personalSensitiveInformation": ""
}

```

- Annotator 2:

```

{
// Croissant core attributes
"sc:description": "LibriSpeech is a corpus of approximately 1000 hours of
16kHz read English speech, prepared by Vassil Panayotov with the assistance of
Daniel Povey. The data is derived from read audiobooks from the LibriVox
project, and has been carefully segmented and aligned.",
"sc:license": "https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.html",

```

```
"sc:name": "librispeech_asr",
"sc:url": "https://huggingface.co/datasets/librispeech_asr",
"sc:creator":
[
{
"@type": "Person",
"name": "Vassil Panayotov",
},
{
"@type": "Person",
"name": "Guoguo Chen",
},
{
"@type": "Person",
"name": "Yoach Lacombe",
},
{
"@type": "Person",
"name": "Daniel Povey",
},
{
"@type": "Person",
"name": "Sanjeev Khudanpur",
}
],
"sc:publisher":
{
"@type": "Person",
"name": "Patrick von Platen",
"url": "https://huggingface.co/patrickvonplaten",
},
"sc:datePublished":
{
"@type": "sc:Date",
"@value": "2022-01-25",
},
"sc:inLanguage": "English",
"cr:citeAs": "@inproceedings{panayotov2015librispeech, title={Librispeech:
an ASR corpus based on public domain audio books}, author={Panayotov, Vassil
and Chen, Guoguo and Povey, Daniel and Khudanpur, Sanjeev},
booktitle={Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP), 2015 IEEE
International Conference on}, pages={5206--5210}, year={2015},
organization={IEEE}}",
"cr:isLiveDataset":
{
```

```

    "@type": "sc:Boolean",
    "@value": "False",
  },
  // RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "The data is derived from read audiobooks from the LibriVox project, and has been carefully segmented and aligned.",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "N/A",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "N/A",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "'The dataset can be used for training, validation, testing, and fine-tuning.'",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "The data has been completely de-identified"
}

```

- **Annotator 3:**

```

{
  // Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "LibriSpeech is a corpus of approximately 1000 hours of 16kHz read English speech. The data is derived from read audiobooks from the LibriVox project, and has been carefully segmented and aligned.",
  "sc:license": "CC BY 4.0",
  "sc:name": "librispeech_asr",
  "sc:url": "https://www.openslr.org/12",
  "sc:creator": "Vassil Panayotov, Daniel Povey",
  "sc:publisher": "Vassil Panayotov, Guoguo Chen, Daniel Povey, and Sanjeev Khudanpur.",
  "sc:datePublished": "2015",
  "sc:inLanguage": "en",
  "cr:citeAs": "@inproceedings{panayotov2015librispeech,
  title={Librispeech: an ASR corpus based on public domain audio books},
  author={Panayotov, Vassil and Chen, Guoguo and Povey, Daniel and Khudanpur, Sanjeev},
  booktitle={Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP), 2015 IEEE International Conference on},
  pages={5206--5210},
  year={2015},
  organization={IEEE}
}
",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "yes",

```

```
// RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "The data is derived from read audiobooks from the LibriVox project, and has been carefully segmented and aligned.",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "LibriVox",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "global volunteers of LibriVox project",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "Speech Recognition",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "The dataset consists of people who have donated their voice online. You agree to not attempt to determine the identity of speakers in this dataset."
}
```

Dataset 2 - MLS dataset

- **Overview of Dataset:**
 - Link: https://huggingface.co/datasets/parler-tts/mls_eng_10k
- **Annotator 1:**

```
{
// Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "MLS dataset is a large multilingual corpus suitable for speech research. The dataset is derived from read audiobooks from LibriVox and consists of 8 languages - English, German, Dutch, Spanish, French, Italian, Portuguese, Polish. It includes about 44.5K hours of English and a total of about 6K hours for other languages.",
  "sc:license": "Creative Commons 4.0",
  "sc:name": "mls_eng_10k",
  "sc:url": "https://huggingface.co/datasets/parler-tts/mls_eng_10k",
  "sc:creator": "Pratap et al",
  "sc:publisher": "ISCA - International Speech Communication Association",
  "sc:datePublished": "December 7, 2020",
  "sc:inLanguage": "English, German, Dutch, Spanish, French, Italian, Portuguese, Polish",
  "cr:citeAs": "@article{Pratap2020MLSAL,
  title={MLS: A Large-Scale Multilingual Dataset for Speech Research},
  author={Vineel Pratap and Qiantong Xu and Anuroop Sriram and Gabriel Synnaeve and Ronan Collobert},
  journal={ArXiv},
  year={2020},
  volume={abs/2012.03411}
}
",
```

```

    "cr:isLiveDataset": "No",
    // RAI attributes
    "rai:dataCollection": "Automatically extraction of text for domains (
gutenberg.org, archive.org, ccel.org and hathitrust.or) and downloaded the text
sources for all the audiobooks in English",
    "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "",
    "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "LibriVox APIs",
    "rai:annotatorDemographics": "",
    "rai:dataUseCases": "For Automated-Speech Recognition (ASR) and
Text-To-Speech (TTS) research",
    "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": ""
}

```

- Annotator 2:

```

{
  // Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "This is a 10K hours subset of English version of the
Multilingual LibriSpeech (MLS) dataset. The data archives were restructured
from the original ones from OpenSLR to make it easier to stream. MLS dataset is
a large multilingual corpus suitable for speech research. The dataset is
derived from read audiobooks from LibriVox and consists of 8 languages -
English, German, Dutch, Spanish, French, Italian, Portuguese, Polish. It
includes about 44.5K hours of English and a total of about 6K hours for other
languages. This dataset includes the 10K hours of English.",
  "sc:license": "https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.html",
  "sc:name": "mls_eng_10k",
  "sc:url": "https://huggingface.co/datasets/parler-tts/mls_eng_10k",
  "sc:creator":
  {
    "@type": "Organization",
    "name": "Parler-TTS",
    "url": "https://huggingface.co/parler-tts"
  },
  "sc:publisher":
  {
    "@type": "Person",
    "name": "Yoach Lacombe",
    "url": "https://huggingface.co/ylocombe"
  },
  "sc:datePublished":
  {

```

```

    "@type": "sc:Date",
    "@value": "2024-03-11",
  },
  "sc:inLanguage": "English",
  "cr:citeAs": "@article{Pratap2020MLSAL, title={MLS: A Large-Scale Multilingual Dataset for Speech Research}, author={Vineel Pratap and Qiantong Xu and Anuroop Sriram and Gabriel Synnaeve and Ronan Collobert}, journal={ArXiv}, year={2020}, volume={abs/2012.03411}}",
  "cr:isLiveDataset":
  {
    "@type": "sc:Boolean",
    "@value": "False",
  },
  // RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "The dataset is derived from read audiobooks from LibriVox and consists of 8 languages - English, German, Dutch, Spanish, French, Italian, Portuguese, Polish.",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "None, a semi-supervised learning approach is followed with pseudo-label generation",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "N/A",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "The dataset can be used for training, validation, testing, and fine-tuning.",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "The data has been completely de-identified"
}

```

- **Annotator 3:**

```

{
  // Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "This is a 10K hours subset of English version of the Multilingual LibriSpeech (MLS) dataset. The data archives were restructured from the original ones from OpenSLR to make it easier to stream. MLS dataset is a large multilingual corpus suitable for speech research. The dataset is derived from read audiobooks from LibriVox and consists of 8 languages - English, German, Dutch, Spanish, French, Italian, Portuguese, Polish. It includes about 44.5K hours of English and a total of about 6K hours for other languages. This dataset card includes the 10K hours of English. Refers to this dataset card for the other languages.",
  "sc:license": "Public Domain, Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License (CC-BY-4.0)",
}

```

```

"sc:name": "parler-tts/mls_eng_10k",
"sc:url": "https://huggingface.co/datasets/parler-tts/mls_eng_10k",
"sc:creator": "Vineel Pratap",
"sc:publisher": "ISCA",
"sc:datePublished": "7 Dec 2020",
"sc:inLanguage": "English",
"cr:citeAs": "@article{Pratap2020MLSAL,
title={MLS: A Large-Scale Multilingual Dataset for Speech Research},
author={Vineel Pratap and Qiantong Xu and Anuroop Sriram and Gabriel Synnaeve
and Ronan Collobert},
journal={ArXiv},
year={2020},
volume={abs/2012.03411}
}",
"cr:isLiveDataset": "No",
// RAI attributes
"rai:dataCollection": "The transcript retrieval process involved finding
the true target label for the audio segments from the source text of audio. To
address challenges with numbers and punctuation in dataset preparation, text
matching with pseudo labels is used to replace numbers, while heuristics are
applied for hyphens and apostrophes; for dataset splits, books are filtered and
speakers are labeled by gender, then split into training, development, and test
sets ensuring speaker balance and duration; additional exclusivity measures are
applied for English datasets; limited supervision datasets are also provided
for each language, comprising various hour-based and minute-based subsets
sampled from available speakers.,
"rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "",
"rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "LibriVox APIs",
"rai:annotatorDemographics": "Automated Tool"; Researchers led the
development of automation tools and software to guide the data development and
processing,
"rai:dataUseCases": "ASR and Text-To-Speech (TTS) research",
"rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "Paper authors/researchers who
conducted the automated data collection"
}

```

Dataset 3 - MMLU dataset

- **Overview of Dataset:**
 - Link: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/cais/mmlu>
- **Annotator 1:**

```
{
```

```

// Croissant core attributes
"sc:description": "This is a massive multitask test consisting of
multiple-choice questions from various branches of knowledge. The test spans
subjects in the humanities, social sciences, hard sciences, and other areas
that are important for some people to learn. This covers 57 tasks including
elementary mathematics, US history, computer science, law, and more. To attain
high accuracy on this test, models must possess extensive world knowledge and
problem solving ability",
"sc:license": "MIT License",
"sc:name": "mmlu",
"sc:url": "https://github.com/hendrycks/test",
"sc:creator":
[
  {
    "@type": "Person",
    "email": "mailto:dan@safe.ai",
    "name": "Dan Hendrycks",
  },
  {
    "@type": "Person",
    "name": "Collin Burns",
  },
  {
    "@type": "Person",
    "name": "Steven Basart",
  },
  {
    "@type": "Person",
    "email": "mailto:andyzou@cmu.edu",
    "name": "Andy Zou",
  },
]
"sc:publisher": "ICLR 2021",
"sc:datePublished": "12/01/2021",
"sc:inLanguage": "English",
"cr:citeAs": "@article{hendryckstest2021,
title={Measuring Massive Multitask Language Understanding},
author={Dan Hendrycks and Collin Burns and Steven Basart and Andy Zou
and Mantas Mazeika and Dawn Song and Jacob Steinhardt},
journal={Proceedings of the International Conference on Learning
Representations (ICLR)},
year={2021}

```

```

    }

    @article{hendrycks2021ethics,
      title={Aligning AI With Shared Human Values},
      author={Dan Hendrycks and Collin Burns and Steven Basart and Andrew
      Critch and Jerry Li and Dawn Song and Jacob Steinhardt},
      journal={Proceedings of the International Conference on Learning
      Representations (ICLR)},
      year={2021}
    }

",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "1",

  // RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "The test includes 57 tasks, mirroring the number of
  Atari games, covering humanities, social sciences, hard sciences, and more.
  Questions were manually gathered by students from online resources, including
  practice exams for GRE, USMLE, and undergraduate courses. Tasks are categorized
  by difficulty levels such as Elementary, High School, College, and
  Professional. 15,908 questions were collected and divided into a few-shot
  development set (5 questions per subject), a validation set (1,540 questions),
  and a test set (14,079 questions)",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Manually",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "Graduate and undergraduate students",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "'A benchmark for assessing language models across a
  diverse set of subjects that humans learn.'",
  """,
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "Not disclosed"
}

```

- **Annotator 2:**

```

{
  // Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "This is a massive multitask test consisting of
  multiple-choice questions from various branches of knowledge. The test spans
  subjects in the humanities, social sciences, hard sciences, and other areas
  that are important for some people to learn. This covers 57 tasks including
  elementary mathematics, US history, computer science, law, and more. To attain

```

```

high accuracy on this test, models must possess extensive world knowledge and
problem solving ability.",
  "sc:license": "MIT",
  "sc:name": "mmlu",
  "sc:url": "https://huggingface.co/datasets/cais/mmlu",
  "sc:creator": "Dan Hendrycks, Collin Burns, Steven Basart, Andy Zou, Mantas
Mazeika, Dawn Song, and Jacob Steinhardt",
  "sc:publisher": "Dan Hendrycks, Collin Burns, Steven Basart, Andy Zou,
Mantas Mazeika, Dawn Song, and Jacob Steinhardt",
  "sc:datePublished": "Jan 2021",
  "sc:inLanguage": "English",
  "cr:citeAs": ["@article{hendryckstest2021, title={Measuring Massive
Multitask Language Understanding}, author={Dan Hendrycks and Collin Burns and
Steven Basart and Andy Zou and Mantas Mazeika and Dawn Song and Jacob
Steinhardt}, journal={Proceedings of the International Conference on Learning
Representations (ICLR)}, year={2021} }", "@article{hendrycks2021ethics,
title={Aligning AI With Shared Human Values}, author={Dan Hendrycks and Collin
Burns and Steven Basart and Andrew Critch and Jerry Li and Dawn Song and Jacob
Steinhardt}, journal={Proceedings of the International Conference on Learning
Representations (ICLR)}, year={2021} }"],
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "false",
  // RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "The dataset collects 15908 questions which were
manually collected by graduate and undergraduate students from freely available
sources online. These include practice questions for tests such as the Graduate
Record Examination and the United States Medical Licensing Examination. It also
includes questions designed for undergraduate courses and questions designed
for readers of Oxford University Press books.",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "None. The questions were already
annotated.",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "None. The questions were already annotated.
Correct answers for the questions were already provided.",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "Multitask Natural Language Understanding",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "NA"
}

```

- Annotator 3

```

{
  // Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "This is a massive multitask test consisting of
multiple-choice questions from various branches of knowledge. The test spans
subjects in the humanities, social sciences, hard sciences, and other areas

```

that are important for some people to learn. This covers 57 tasks including elementary mathematics, US history, computer science, law, and more. To attain high accuracy on this test, models must possess extensive world knowledge and problem solving ability.

```
A complete list of tasks: ['abstract_algebra', 'anatomy', 'astronomy',
'business_ethics', 'clinical_knowledge', 'college_biology',
'college_chemistry', 'college_computer_science', 'college_mathematics',
'college_medicine', 'college_physics', 'computer_security',
'conceptual_physics', 'econometrics', 'electrical_engineering',
'elementary_mathematics', 'formal_logic', 'global_facts',
'high_school_biology', 'high_school_chemistry', 'high_school_computer_science',
'high_school_european_history', 'high_school_geography',
'high_school_government_and_politics', 'high_school_macroeconomics',
'high_school_mathematics', 'high_school_microeconomics', 'high_school_physics',
'high_school_psychology', 'high_school_statistics', 'high_school_us_history',
'high_school_world_history', 'human_aging', 'human_sexuality',
'international_law', 'jurisprudence', 'logical_fallacies', 'machine_learning',
'management', 'marketing', 'medical_genetics', 'miscellaneous',
'moral_disputes', 'moral_scenarios', 'nutrition', 'philosophy', 'prehistory',
'professional_accounting', 'professional_law', 'professional_medicine',
'professional_psychology', 'public_relations', 'security_studies', 'sociology',
'us_foreign_policy', 'virology', 'world_religions']
```

```
",
  "sc:license": "https://github.com/hendrycks/test/blob/master/LICENSE",
  "sc:name": "mmlu",
  "sc:url": "https://github.com/hendrycks/test/blob/master/README.md",
  "sc:creator": "Dan Hendrycks, Collin Burns, Steven Basart, Andy Zou, Mantas
Mazeika, Dawn Song, Jacob Steinhardt",
  "sc:publisher": " Dan Hendrycks",
  "sc:datePublished": "7 Sep 2020",
  "sc:inLanguage": "English",
  "cr:citeAs": " @article{hendryckstest2021,
    title={Measuring Massive Multitask Language Understanding},
    author={Dan Hendrycks and Collin Burns and Steven Basart and Andy Zou and
Mantas Mazeika and Dawn Song and Jacob Steinhardt},
    journal={Proceedings of the International Conference on Learning
Representations (ICLR)},
    year={2021}
  }
",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "false",
// RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "We create a massive multitask test consisting of
multiple-choice questions from various branches of knowledge. The test spans
```

subjects in the humanities, social sciences, hard sciences, and other areas that are important for some people to learn. There are 57 tasks in total, which is also the number of Atari games (Bellemare et al., 2013), all of which are listed in Appendix B. The questions in the dataset were manually collected by graduate and undergraduate students from freely available sources online. These include practice questions for tests such as the Graduate Record Examination and the United States Medical Licensing Examination. It also includes questions designed for undergraduate courses and questions designed for readers of Oxford University Press books. Some tasks cover a subject, like psychology, but at a specific level of difficulty, such as “Elementary,” “High School,” “College,” or “Professional.” For example, the “Professional Psychology” task draws on questions from freely available practice questions for the Examination for Professional Practice in Psychology, while the “High School Psychology” task has questions like those from Advanced Placement Psychology examinations. We collected 15908 questions in total, which we split into a few-shot development set, a validation set, and a test set. The few-shot development set has 5 questions per subject, the validation set may be used for selecting hyperparameters and is made of 1540 questions, and the test set has 14079 questions. Each subject contains 100 test examples at the minimum, which is longer than most exams designed to assess people. Human-level accuracy on this test varies. Unspecialized humans from Amazon Mechanical Turk obtain 34.5% accuracy on this test. Meanwhile, expert-level performance can be far higher. For example, real-world test-taker human accuracy at the 95th percentile is around 87% for US Medical Licensing Examinations, and these questions make up our “Professional Medicine” task. If we take the 95th percentile human test-taker accuracy for exams that build up our test, and if we make an educated guess when such information is unavailable, we then estimate that expert-level accuracy is approximately 89.8%. Since our test aggregates different subjects and several levels of difficulty, we measure more than straightforward commonsense or narrow linguistic understanding. Instead, we measure arbitrary real-world text understanding. Since models are pretrained on the Internet, this enables us to test how well they can extract useful knowledge from massive corpora. Future models that use this test could be single models or a mixture of experts model. To succeed at our test, future models should be well-rounded, possess extensive world knowledge, and develop expert-level problem solving ability. These properties make the test likely to be an enduring and informative goalpost.”

```
"rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "NA",  
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "manually collected from freely available  
sources online",  
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "graduate and undergraduate students",  
  "rai:dataUseCases": "Testing Multimodal Understanding",  
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "NA"  
}
```

Dataset 4 - FLORES dataset

- **Overview of Dataset:**
 - Link: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/flores>
- **Annotator 1:**

```
{
// Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "Evaluation datasets for low-resource machine
translation: Nepali-English and Sinhala-English.",
  "sc:license": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/",
  "sc:name": "flores",
  "sc:url":
"https://github.com/facebookresearch/flores/tree/main/previous_releases/floresv
1",
  "sc:creator": "Guzm\ '{a}n, Francisco and Chen, Peng-Jen and Ott, Myle and
Pino, Juan and Lample, Guillaume and Koehn, Philipp and Chaudhary, Vishrav and
Ranzato, Marc'Aurelio",
  "sc:publisher": "Guzm\ '{a}n, Francisco and Chen, Peng-Jen and Ott, Myle and
Pino, Juan and Lample, Guillaume and Koehn, Philipp and Chaudhary, Vishrav and
Ranzato, Marc'Aurelio",
  "sc:datePublished": "February 4, 2019",
  "sc:inLanguage": "Nepali-English and Sinhala-English",
  "cr:citeAs": "@inproceedings{,
  title={Two New Evaluation Datasets for Low-Resource Machine Translation:
Nepali-English and Sinhala-English},
  author={Guzm\ '{a}n, Francisco and Chen, Peng-Jen and Ott, Myle and Pino, Juan
and Lample, Guillaume and Koehn, Philipp and Chaudhary, Vishrav and Ranzato,
Marc'Aurelio},
  journal={arXiv preprint arXiv:1902.01382},
  year={2019}
}",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "true",
// RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "Sentences were randomly extracted from Wikipedia
pages in each language and translated by professional translators. Wikipedia
pages in English, Nepali and Sinhala ({en,ne,si}.wikipedia.org) were collected
from a Wikipedia crawl of early May 2018. To select sentences for translation,
Wikipedia documents were filtered to only retain the top 25 documents that
contain the largest number of candidate sentences in each source language.
Candidate sentences were sentences that matched the intended language according
to a language model and had 50 to 150 words. Afterwards, a manual filter was
applied. Sentences in English must have started with an uppercase letter and
ended in a period. Sentences in Nepali and Sinhala were filtered with a regular
```

expression to avoid symbols such as bullet points, repeated dashes or periods and avoid ASCII characters. From the filtered documents, 2,500 random sentences were sampled for each language. English was translated to Nepali and Sinhala, while Nepali and Sinhala were only translated to English. Each string was translated twice by different translators. Both automatic and manual methods were used to detect high and low quality translations. Automatic checks were used to find low quality translations which were sent for rework. The original and reworked passing results were then sent for manual checking. Results that passed automatic and manual checking were used to build the test sets. Automatic quality checks include: 1) applying a count-based n-gram language model trained on Wikipedia monolingual data and removing translations that have perplexity above 3000.0 (English translations only), 2) removing translations that had sentence-level char-BLEU score between the two generated translations below 15 or above 90, 3) removing sentences that contained at least 33% transliterated words, 4) removing translations with at least 50% of words copied from the source sentence, and 5) removing translations that contained more than 50% out-of-vocabulary ratio or 5 total out-of-vocabulary words in the sentences (English translations only). For manual translations, three different raters were asked to rate the sentences from 0 to 100 according to the perceived translation quality. To ensure rating consistency, any evaluation in which the range of scores among the three reviewers was above 30 points was rejected. A fourth rater broke ties by replacing the most diverging translation rating with the new one. This process was repeated until convergence was reached. For each translation, the average score over all raters was taken. Translations whose scores were below 70 were rejected. Finally, an Amazon Mechanical Turk monolingual task was used to judge the fluency of English translations. Five independent human annotators were used to rate the fluency of each English translation from 1 to 5, where an average score less than 3 resulted in the translation being rejected. The resulting passing translations were used to build dev (tune), devtest (validation) and test (test) datasets.",

```
"rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "May 1, 2018 T00:00:00 to February 4, 2019 T00:00:00",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Professional translators were given translation tasks and Amazon Mechanical Turk workers were given data quality tasks.",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "Translators were professionals.",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "The dataset is meant for evaluation settings and can be used for fine-tuning, validation, and testing."
",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "N/A"
}
```

- Annotator 2:

```

{
// Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "The FLORES dataset was introduced to address the
challenge of evaluating machine translation systems for low-resource language
pairs, specifically Nepali-English and Sinhala-English[1]. These languages were
chosen because they present a significant morphological and syntactic
difference from English, and there is a scarcity of parallel data available for
them[2]. The dataset offers a new benchmark for the machine translation
community, particularly focusing on the translation performance for these
low-resource language pairs. It consists of sentences extracted from Wikipedia
articles, professionally translated, with the aim of providing a challenging
testbed for state-of-the-art machine translation systems across different
training settings including fully supervised, weakly supervised,
semi-supervised, and fully unsupervised learning[3].
The dataset is structured to include a variety of sentences covering a broad
range of topics, such as history, law, sports, and general knowledge,
increasing the difficulty and requiring domain-independent models
",
  "sc:license": "CC-BY-SA 4.0",
  "sc:name": "The FLORES Evaluation Datasets for Low-Resource Machine
Translation: Nepali-English and Sinhala-English",
  "sc:url": "https://github.com/facebookresearch/flores",
  "sc:creator":
  [
    {
      "@type": "Person",
      "name": "Francisco Guzman",
      "email": "mailto:fguzman@fb.com",
      "affiliation": {
        "@type": "Organization",
        "Name": "Facebook Applied Machine Learning"
      }
    },
    {
      "@type": "Person",
      "name": "Peng-Jen Chen",
      "email": "mailto:pipibjc@fb.com",
      "affiliation": {
        "@type": "Organization",
        "Name": "Facebook AI Research"
      }
    }
  ],
}

```

```
{
  "@type": "Person",
  "name": "Mayle Ott",
  "email": "mailto:myleott@fb.com",
  "affiliation": {
    "@type": "Organization",
    "Name": "Facebook AI Research"
  }
},
{
  "@type": "Person",
  "name": "Juan Pino",
  "email": "mailto:juancarabina@fb.com",
  "affiliation": {
    "@type": "Organization",
    "Name": "Facebook Applied Machine Learning"
  }
},
],
"sc:publisher": "GitHub",
"sc:datePublished": "2022-06-30",
"sc:inLanguage":
[
  {
    "name": "Nepali",
    "alternateName": "ne"
  },
  {
    "name": "English",
    "alternateName": "en"
  },
  {
    "name": "Sinhala",
    "alternateName": "si"
  }
],
"cr:citeAs": "@article{nllb2022,
```

author = {NLLB Team, Marta R. Costa-jussà, James Cross, Onur Çelebi, Maha Elbayad, Kenneth Heafield, Kevin Heffernan, Elahe Kalbassi, Janice Lam, Daniel Licht, Jean Maillard, Anna Sun, Skyler Wang, Guillaume Wenzek, Al Youngblood, Bapi Akula, Loic Barrault, Gabriel Mejia Gonzalez, Prangthip Hansanti, John Hoffman, Semarley Jarrett, Kaushik Ram Sadagopan, Dirk Rowe, Shannon Spruit, Chau Tran, Pierre Andrews, Necip Fazil Ayan, Shruti Bhosale, Sergey Edunov, Angela Fan, Cynthia Gao, Vedanuj Goswami, Francisco Guzmán, Philipp Koehn,

```

Alexandre Mourachko, Christophe Ropers, Safiyyah Saleem, Holger Schwenk, Jeff
Wang},
  title      = {No Language Left Behind: Scaling Human-Centered Machine
Translation},
  year       = {2022}
}
",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "1",
// RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "Sentences were extracted from Wikipedia articles,
specifically chosen to span a diverse range of domains such as history, law,
and sports, amongst others, to ensure a broad coverage of topics. This
diversity is crucial for the dataset to challenge and accurately evaluate
domain-independent machine translation models

The selected sentences were then professionally translated, underscoring the
importance of accurate and fluent translations. The process involved automatic
and manual checks to ensure the translations met high-quality standards.
Specifically, the dataset underwent careful manual review, which focused on
assessing translation quality and fluency",
",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Unknown",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "Unknown",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "Evaluating Machine Translation Systems", "Research in
Low-Resource Language Translation",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "unknown"
}

```

- Annotator 3 -

```

{
// Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "Evaluation datasets for low-resource machine
translation: Nepali-English and Sinhala-English.",
  "sc:license": "cc-by-4.0",
  "sc:name": "FLORES",
  "sc:url": "https://github.com/facebookresearch/flores",
  "sc:creator": ["Francisco Guzman", "Peng-Jen Chen", "Myle Ott", "Juan
Pino", "Guillaume Lample", "Philipp Koehn", " Vishrav Chaudhary", "Marc'Aurelio
Ranzato"],
  "sc:publisher": ["Francisco Guzman", "Peng-Jen Chen", "Myle Ott", "Juan

```

```
Pino", "Guillaume Lample", "Philipp Koehn", " Vishrav Chaudhary", "Marc'Aurelio
Ranzato"],
  "sc:datePublished": "2019",
  "sc:inLanguage": ["English", "Nepali", "Sinhala"],
  "cr:citeAs": "@inproceedings{guzman-etal-2019-flores,
  title = "The {FLORES} Evaluation Datasets for Low-Resource Machine
Translation: {N}epali{--}{E}nglish and {S}inhala{--}{E}nglish",
  author = "Guzm{\'}a)n, Francisco and
  Chen, Peng-Jen and
  Ott, Myle and
  Pino, Juan and
  Lample, Guillaume and
  Koehn, Philipp and
  Chaudhary, Vishrav and
  Ranzato, Marc{\'}Aurelio",
  editor = "Inui, Kentaro and
  Jiang, Jing and
  Ng, Vincent and
  Wan, Xiaojun",
  booktitle = "Proceedings of the 2019 Conference on Empirical Methods in
Natural Language Processing and the 9th International Joint Conference on
Natural Language Processing (EMNLP-IJCNLP)",
  month = nov,
  year = "2019",
  address = "Hong Kong, China",
  publisher = "Association for Computational Linguistics",
  url = "https://aclanthology.org/D19-1632",
  doi = "10.18653/v1/D19-1632",
  pages = "6098--6111",
  abstract = "For machine translation, a vast majority of language pairs in
the world are considered low-resource because they have little parallel data
available. Besides the technical challenges of learning with limited
supervision, it is difficult to evaluate methods trained on low-resource
language pairs because of the lack of freely and publicly available benchmarks.
In this work, we introduce the FLORES evaluation datasets for Nepali{--}English
and Sinhala{--} English, based on sentences translated from Wikipedia. Compared
to English, these are languages with very different morphology and syntax, for
which little out-of-domain parallel data is available and for which relatively
large amounts of monolingual data are freely available. We describe our process
to collect and cross-check the quality of translations, and we report baseline
performance using several learning settings: fully supervised, weakly
supervised, semi-supervised, and fully unsupervised. Our experiments
demonstrate that current state-of-the-art methods perform rather poorly on this
benchmark, posing a challenge to the research community working on low-resource
MT. Data and code to reproduce our experiments are available at
```

```

\url{https://github.com/facebookresearch/flores}.",
}
",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "false",
  // RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "The dataset was built by selecting sentences from
wikipedia articles in English, Nepali and Sinhala. Candidate sentences were
filtered by quality and translated twice by human translators. Poor
translations were filtered out by automatic and human quality checks.",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "2018/05",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": ["unknown", "unknown", "AMT"],
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "unknown",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "evaluation",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "none. the dataset contains translation
pairs from wikipedia"
}

```

Dataset 5 - CIFAR dataset

- **Overview of Dataset 1:**
 - Link: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/cifar10>
- **Annotator 1:**

```

{
  // Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "The CIFAR-10 dataset consists of 60000 32x32 colour
images in 10 classes, with 6000 images per class. There are 50000 training
images and 10000 test images. The dataset is divided into five training batches
and one test batch, each with 10000 images. The test batch contains exactly
1000 randomly-selected images from each class. The training batches contain the
remaining images in random order, but some training batches may contain more
images from one class than another. Between them, the training batches contain
exactly 5000 images from each class.",
  "sc:license": "NA",
  "sc:name": "CIFAR-10",
  "sc:url": "https://www.cs.toronto.edu/~kriz/cifar.html",
  "sc:creator": "Alex Krizhevsky",
  "sc:publisher": "University of Toronto",
  "sc:datePublished": "April 8, 2009",
  "sc:inLanguage": "English",
  "cr:citeAs": "Learning Multiple Layers of Features from Tiny Images, Alex
Krizhevsky, 2009.",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "false",
}

```

```

// RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "The tiny images dataset on which we based all of our experiments was collected by colleagues at MIT and NYU over the span of six months; it is described in detail in [14]. They assembled it by searching the web for images of every non-abstract English noun in the lexical database WordNet[15, 8]. They used several search engines, including Google, Flickr, and Altavista and kept roughly the first 3000 results for each search term. After collecting all the images for a particular search term, they removed perfect duplicates and images in which an excessively large portion of the pixels were white, as they tended to be synthetic figures rather than natural images. The search term used to find an image provides it with a rough label, although it is extremely unreliable due to the nature of online image search technology. In total, the dataset contains 80 million colour images downsampled to 32 × 32 and spread out across 79000 search terms. Most of our experiments with unsupervised learning were performed on a subset of about 2 million images.",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "6 months",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Unknown",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "students",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "image-classification, Training, unsupervised pretraining",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "Unknown"
}

```

- **Annotator 2:**

```

{
// Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "The CIFAR-10 dataset consists of 60000 32x32 colour images in 10 classes, with 6000 images per class. There are 50000 training images and 10000 test images. The dataset is divided into five training batches and one test batch, each with 10000 images. The test batch contains exactly 1000 randomly-selected images from each class. The training batches contain the remaining images in random order, but some training batches may contain more images from one class than another. Between them, the training batches contain exactly 5000 images from each class.",
  "sc:license": "Unknown",
  "sc:name": "cifar10",
  "sc:url": "https://huggingface.co/datasets/cifar10",
  "sc:creator": "Alex Krizhevsky",
  "sc:publisher": "https://www.cs.toronto.edu/",
  "sc:datePublished": "2009",
  "sc:inLanguage": "English",

```

```

"cr:citeAs": "@TECHREPORT{Krizhevsky09learningmultiple,
author = {Alex Krizhevsky},
title = {Learning multiple layers of features from tiny images},
institution = {},
year = {2009}}",
"cr:isLiveDataset": "False",
// RAI attributes
"rai:dataCollection": "Groups at MIT and NYU have collected a dataset of
millions of tiny color images from the web. It is, in principle, an excellent
dataset for unsupervised training of deep generative models, but previous
researchers who have tried this have found it difficult to learn a good set of
filters from the images. We show how to train a multi-layer generative model
that learns to extract meaningful features which resemble those found in the
human visual cortex. Using a novel parallelization algorithm to distribute
the work among multiple machines connected on a network, we show how training
such a model can be done in reasonable time. A second problematic aspect of the
tiny images dataset is that there are no reliable class labels which makes it
hard to use for object recognition experiments. We created two sets of reliable
labels. The CIFAR-10 set has 6000 examples of each of 10 classes and the
CIFAR-100 set has 600 examples of each of 100 non-overlapping classes. Using
these labels, we show that object recognition is significantly improved by
pre-training a layer of features on a large set of unlabeled tiny images.",
"rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "six months",
"rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Unknown",
"rai:annotatorDemographics": "Groups at MIT and NYU",
"rai:dataUseCases": "image recognition and classification",
"rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "Unknown"
}

```

- **Annotator 3:**

```

{
// Croissant core attributes
"sc:description": "The CIFAR-10 dataset is for image classification task
and consists of 60000 32x32 colour images in 10 classes, with 6000 images per
class.",
"sc:license": "Unknown",
"sc:name": "CIFAR-10",
"sc:url": "https://www.cs.toronto.edu/~kriz/cifar.html",
"sc:creator": "Alex Krizhevsky, Vinod Nair, and Geoffrey Hinton",
"sc:publisher": "Alex Krizhevsky",
"sc:datePublished": "2009",

```

```

"sc:inLanguage": "en",
"cr:citeAs": "@TECHREPORT{Krizhevsky09learningmultiple,
author = {Alex Krizhevsky},
title = {Learning multiple layers of features from tiny images},
institution = {},
year = {2009}
}
",
"cr:isLiveDataset": "yes",
// RAI attributes
"rai:dataCollection": "Students were hired to label a subset of the tiny
images dataset. The labeled subset collected consisted of ten classes of
objects, each containing 6000 images. The classes include airplane, automobile
(excluding truck or pickup truck), bird, cat, deer, dog, frog, horse, ship, and
truck (excluding pickup truck). Each image in the dataset already had a noisy
label (the search term used to find the image). The task for the labelers was
to filter out the mislabeled images. They were assigned a class and tasked with
examining all images found with that class as the search term. Additionally,
since the dataset contained approximately 3000 images per search term, the
labelers were instructed to examine all images found with a search term that is
a hyponym (as defined by WordNet) of the main search term. For example, some
hyponyms of "ship" are "cargo ship," "ocean liner," and "frigate." The labelers
were directed to reject images that did not belong to their assigned class.",
"rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
"rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Unknown",
"rai:annotatorDemographics": "students",
"rai:dataUseCases": "The CIFAR-10 dataset is primarily used for image
classification tasks and serves as a benchmark for evaluating machine learning
algorithms in computer vision. It is also employed in transfer learning
experiments, educational settings, and research in image processing techniques.
",
"rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "NA"
}

```

Dataset 6 - DOLLY dataset

- **Overview of Dataset:**
 - Link: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/databricks/databricks-dolly-15k>
- **Annotator 1:**

```
{
```

```
// Croissant core attributes
```

```
"sc:description": "databricks-dolly-15k contains 15,000 high-quality human-generated prompt / response pairs specifically designed for instruction tuning large language models.",  
"sc:license": "Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 3.0 Unported License",  
"sc:name": "databricks/databricks-dolly-15k",  
"sc:url": "https://huggingface.co/datasets/databricks/databricks-dolly-15k",  
"sc:creator": "databricks",  
"sc:publisher": "huggingface",  
"sc:datePublished": "June 30, 2023",  
"sc:inLanguage": "English",  
"cr:citeAs": "Mike Conover and Matt Hayes and Ankit Mathur and Jianwei Xie and Jun Wan and Sam Shah and Ali Ghodsi and Patrick Wendell and Matei Zaharia and Reynold Xin, Free Dolly: Introducing the World's First Truly Open Instruction-Tuned LLM, https://www.databricks.com/blog/2023/04/12/dolly-first-open-commercially-viable-instruction-tuned-llm, 2023",  
"cr:isLiveDataset": "False",
```

```
// RAI attributes
```

```
"rai:dataCollection": "Human-generated data: Databricks employees were invited to create prompt / response pairs in each of eight different instruction categories. Wikipedia: For instruction categories that require an annotator to consult a reference text (information extraction, closed QA, summarization) contributors selected passages from Wikipedia for particular subsets of instruction categories. No guidance was given to annotators as to how to select the target passages.",  
"rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",  
"rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "To create a record, employees were given a brief description of the annotation task as well as examples of the types of prompts typical of each annotation task. Guidelines were succinct by design so as to encourage a high task completion rate, possibly at the cost of rigorous compliance to an annotation rubric that concretely and reliably operationalizes the specific task. Caveat emptor.
```

The annotation guidelines for each of the categories are as follows:

Creative Writing: Write a question or instruction that requires a creative, open-ended written response. The instruction should be reasonable to ask of a person with general world knowledge and should not require searching. In this task, your prompt should give very specific instructions to follow. Constraints, instructions, guidelines, or requirements all work, and the more of them the better.

Closed QA: Write a question or instruction that requires factually correct response based on a passage of text from Wikipedia. The question can be complex and can involve human-level reasoning capabilities, but should not require special knowledge. To create a question for this task include both the text of the question as well as the reference text in the form.

Open QA: Write a question that can be answered using general world knowledge or at most a single search. This task asks for opinions and facts about the world at large and does not

provide any reference text for consultation.

Summarization: Give a summary of a paragraph from Wikipedia. Please don't ask questions that will require more than 3-5 minutes to answer. To create a question for this task include both the text of the question as well as the reference text in the form.

Information Extraction: These questions involve reading a paragraph from Wikipedia and extracting information from the passage. Everything required to produce an answer (e.g. a list, keywords etc) should be included in the passages. To create a question for this task include both the text of the question as well as the reference text in the form.

Classification: These prompts contain lists or examples of entities to be classified, e.g. movie reviews, products, etc. In this task the text or list of entities under consideration is contained in the prompt (e.g. there is no reference text.). You can choose any categories for classification you like, the more diverse the better.

Brainstorming: Think up lots of examples in response to a question asking to brainstorm ideas.

```
",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "Databricks Employees",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "While immediately valuable for instruction fine tuning large language models, as a corpus of human-generated instruction prompts, this dataset also presents a valuable opportunity for synthetic data generation in the methods outlined in the Self-Instruct paper. For example, contributor--generated prompts could be submitted as few-shot examples to a large open language model to generate a corpus of millions of examples of instructions in each of the respective InstructGPT categories.
```

Likewise, both the instructions and responses present fertile ground for data augmentation. A paraphrasing model might be used to restate each prompt or short responses, with the resulting text associated to the respective ground-truth sample. Such an approach might provide a form of regularization on the dataset that could allow for more robust instruction-following behavior in models derived from these synthetic datasets.

```
",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "This dataset contains public information (e.g., some information from Wikipedia). To our knowledge, there are no private person's personal identifiers or sensitive information."
```

```
}
```

- **Annotator 2:**

```
{
// Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "databricks-dolly-15k is an open source dataset of instruction-following records generated by thousands of Databricks employees to enable large language models to exhibit the magical interactivity of
```

```

ChatGPT",
  "sc:license": "Copyright (2023) Databricks, Inc. This dataset was developed
at Databricks (https://www.databricks.com) and its use is subject to the CC
BY-SA 3.0 license.",
  "sc:name": "databricks-dolly-15k",
  "sc:url":
"https://huggingface.co/datasets/databricks/databricks-dolly-15k",
  "sc:creator": "Databricks",
  "sc:publisher": "Databricks",
  "sc:datePublished": "2023",
  "sc:inLanguage": "American English",
  "cr:citeAs": "@online{DatabricksBlog2023DollyV2,
author    = {Mike Conover and Matt Hayes and Ankit Mathur and Jianwei Xie
and Jun Wan and Sam Shah and Ali Ghodsi and Patrick Wendell and Matei Zaharia
and Reynold Xin},
title     = {Free Dolly: Introducing the World's First Truly Open
Instruction-Tuned LLM},
year      = {2023},
url       =

{https://www.databricks.com/blog/2023/04/12/dolly-first-open-commercially-viable-instruction-tuned-llm},
urldate   = {2023-06-30}
}
",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "yes",
// RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "Databricks employees were invited to create prompt /
response pairs in each of eight different instruction categories, including the
seven outlined in the InstructGPT paper, as well as an open-ended free-form
category. The contributors were instructed to avoid using information from any
source on the web with the exception of Wikipedia (for particular subsets of
instruction categories), and explicitly instructed to avoid using generative AI
in formulating instructions or responses. Examples of each behavior were
provided to motivate the types of questions and instructions appropriate to
each category. Halfway through the data generation process, contributors were
given the option of answering questions posed by other contributors. They were
asked to rephrase the original question and only select questions they could be
reasonably expected to answer correctly. For certain categories contributors
were asked to provide reference texts copied from Wikipedia. Reference text
(indicated by the context field in the actual dataset) may contain bracketed
Wikipedia citation numbers (e.g. [42]) which we recommend users remove for
downstream applications.
",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Unknown",

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"rai:annotatorDemographics": "Databricks employees",
"rai:dataUseCases": "brainstorming, classification, closed QA, generation,
information extraction, open QA, and summarization",
"rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "This dataset contains public
information (e.g., some information from Wikipedia). To our knowledge, there
are no private person's personal identifiers or sensitive information."
}

```

- **Annotator 3:**

```

{
// Croissant core attributes
"sc:description": "databricks-dolly-15k is an open source dataset of
instruction-following records generated by thousands of Databricks employees in
several of the behavioral categories outlined in the InstructGPT
(https://arxiv.org/pdf/2203.02155) paper, including brainstorming,
classification, closed QA, generation, information extraction, open QA, and
summarization.

This dataset can be used for any purpose, whether academic or commercial, under
the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 3.0 Unported
License.",
"sc:license": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/",
"sc:name": "databricks/databricks-dolly-15k",
"sc:url":
"https://huggingface.co/datasets/databricks/databricks-dolly-15k",
"sc:creator": "Databricks, Inc.",
"sc:publisher": "Databricks, Inc.",
"sc:datePublished": "April 12, 2023",
"sc:inLanguage": "American English",
"cr:citeAs": "@online{DatabricksBlog2023DollyV2,
author = {Mike Conover and Matt Hayes and Ankit Mathur and Jianwei Xie
and Jun Wan and Sam Shah and Ali Ghodsi and Patrick Wendell and Matei Zaharia
and Reynold Xin},
title = {Free Dolly: Introducing the World's First Truly Open
Instruction-Tuned LLM},
year = {2023},
url =
{https://www.databricks.com/blog/2023/04/12/dolly-first-open-commercially-viable-instruction-tuned-llm},
urldate = {2023-06-30}
}",
}

```

```
"cr:isLiveDataset": "false",
```

```
// RAI attributes
```

```
"rai:dataCollection": "databricks-dolly-15k is a corpus of more than 15,000 records generated by thousands of Databricks employees to enable large language models to exhibit the magical interactivity of ChatGPT. Databricks employees were invited to create prompt / response pairs in each of eight different instruction categories, including the seven outlined in the InstructGPT paper, as well as an open-ended free-form category. The contributors were instructed to avoid using information from any source on the web with the exception of Wikipedia (for particular subsets of instruction categories), and explicitly instructed to avoid using generative AI in formulating instructions or responses. Examples of each behavior were provided to motivate the types of questions and instructions appropriate to each category.
```

Halfway through the data generation process, contributors were given the option of answering questions posed by other contributors. They were asked to rephrase the original question and only select questions they could be reasonably expected to answer correctly.

```
For certain categories contributors were asked to provide reference texts copied from Wikipedia. Reference text (indicated by the context field in the actual dataset) may contain bracketed Wikipedia citation numbers (e.g. [42]) which we recommend users remove for downstream applications.",
```

```
"rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "March and April 2023",
```

```
"rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Unknown",
```

```
"rai:annotatorDemographics": "Databricks employees",
```

```
"rai:dataUseCases": "While immediately valuable for instruction fine tuning large language models, as a corpus of human-generated instruction prompts, this dataset also presents a valuable opportunity for synthetic data generation in the methods outlined in the Self-Instruct paper. For example, contributor--generated prompts could be submitted as few-shot examples to a large open language model to generate a corpus of millions of examples of instructions in each of the respective InstructGPT categories.
```

Likewise, both the instructions and responses present fertile ground for data augmentation. A paraphrasing model might be used to restate each prompt or short responses, with the resulting text associated to the respective ground-truth sample. Such an approach might provide a form of regularization on the dataset that could allow for more robust instruction-following behavior in models derived from these synthetic datasets.",

```
"rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "Unknown"
```

```
}
```

Dataset 7 - MSCOCO dataset

- **Overview of Dataset:**
 - Link: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/shunk031/MSCOCO>
- **Annotator 1:**

```
{
// Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "COCO is a large-scale object detection, segmentation,
and captioning dataset. COCO has several features:

Object segmentation
Recognition in context
Superpixel stuff segmentation
330K images (>200K labeled)
1.5 million object instances
80 object categories
91 stuff categories
5 captions per image
250,000 people with keypoints
",
  "sc:license": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/",
  "sc:name": "Coco",
  "sc:url": "https://cocodataset.org/#home",
  "sc:creator": "Tsung-Yi Lin Google Brain
Genevieve Patterson MSR, Trash TV
Matteo R. Ronchi Caltech
Yin Cui Google
Michael Maire TTI-Chicago
Serge Belongie Cornell Tech
Lubomir Bourdev WaveOne, Inc.
Ross Girshick FAIR
James Hays Georgia Tech
Pietro Perona Caltech
Deva Ramanan CMU
Larry Zitnick FAIR
Piotr Dollár FAIR
",
  "sc:publisher": "cocodataset.org",
  "sc:datePublished": "Unknown",
  "sc:inLanguage": "English",
  "cr:citeAs": "@inproceedings{lin2014microsoft,
title={Microsoft coco: Common objects in context},
author={Lin, Tsung-Yi and Maire, Michael and Belongie, Serge and Hays, James
```

```
and Perona, Pietro and Ramanan, Deva and Doll{\`a}r, Piotr and Zitnick, C
Lawrence},
  booktitle={Computer Vision--ECCV 2014: 13th European Conference, Zurich,
Switzerland, September 6-12, 2014, Proceedings, Part V 13},
  pages={740--755},
  year={2014},
  organization={Springer}
}
",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "false",
```

```
// RAI attributes
```

```
"rai:dataCollection": "The selection of object categories is a non-trivial
exercise.
```

The categories must form a representative set of all categories, be relevant to practical applications and occur with high enough frequency to enable the collection of a large dataset. Other important decisions are whether to include both “thing” and “stuff” categories [39] and whether fine-grained [31], [1] and object-part categories should be included. “Thing” categories include objects for which individual instances may be easily labeled (person, chair, car) where “stuff” categories include materials and objects with no clear boundaries (sky, street, grass). Since we are primarily interested in precise localization of object instances, we decided to only include “thing” categories and not “stuff.” However, since “stuff” categories can provide significant contextual information, we believe the future labeling of “stuff” categories would be beneficial.

The specificity of object categories can vary significantly. For instance, a dog could be a member of the “mammal”, “dog”, or “German shepherd” categories. To enable the practical collection of a significant number of instances per category, we chose to limit our dataset to entry-level categories, i.e. category labels that are commonly used by humans when describing objects (dog, chair, person). It is also possible that some object categories may be parts of other object categories. For instance, a face may be part of a person. We anticipate the inclusion of object-part categories (face, hands, wheels) would be beneficial for many real-world applications. We used several sources to collect entry-level object categories of “things.” We first compiled a list of categories by combining categories from PASCAL VOC [2] and a subset of the 1200 most frequently used words

that denote visually identifiable objects [40]. To further augment our set of candidate categories, several children ranging in ages from 4 to 8 were asked to name every object they see in indoor and outdoor environments.

The final 272 candidates may be found in the appendix.

Finally, the co-authors voted on a 1 to 5 scale for each category taking into account how commonly they occur, their usefulness for practical applications, and their diversity relative to other categories. The final selection of categories attempts to pick categories with high

votes, while keeping the number of categories per supercategory (animals, vehicles, furniture, etc.) balanced. Categories for which obtaining a large number of instances

(greater than 5,000) was difficult were also removed.

To ensure backwards compatibility all categories from PASCAL VOC [2] are also included. Our final list of 91 proposed categories is in Fig. 5(a).

Given the list of object categories, our next goal was to collect a set of candidate images. We may roughly group images into three types, Fig. 2: iconic-object images [41], iconic-scene images [3] and non-iconic images. Typical iconic-object images have a single large object in a canonical perspective centered in the image, Fig. 2(a). Iconic-scene images are shot from canonical viewpoints and commonly lack people, Fig. 2(b). Iconic images have the benefit that they may be easily found by directly searching for specific categories using Google or Bing image search. While iconic images generally provide high quality object instances, they can lack important contextual information and non-canonical viewpoints.

Our goal was to collect a dataset such that a majority of images are non-iconic, Fig. 2(c). It has been shown that datasets containing more non-iconic images are better at generalizing [42]. We collected non-iconic images using two strategies. First as popularized by PASCAL VOC [2], we collected images from Flickr which tends to have fewer iconic images. Flickr contains photos uploaded by amateur photographers with searchable metadata and keywords. Second, we did not search for object categories in isolation. A search for “dog” will tend to return iconic images of large, centered dogs. However, if we searched for pairwise combinations of object categories, such as “dog + car” we found many more non-iconic images. Surprisingly, these images typically do not just contain the two categories specified in the search, but numerous other

categories as well. To further supplement our dataset we also searched for scene/object category pairs, see the appendix. We downloaded at most 5 photos taken by a single photographer within a short time window. In the rare cases in which enough images could not be found, we searched for single categories and performed an explicit filtering stage to remove iconic images. The result is a collection of 328,000 images with rich contextual relationships between objects as shown in Figs. 2(c) and 6.

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  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Amazon's Mechanical Turk (AMT)",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "Unknown",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "object detection, segmentation, captioning",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "Unknown"
}
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- **Annotator 2:**

```
{
// Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "COCO is a large-scale object detection, segmentation,
and captioning dataset.",
  "sc:license": "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License for annotations,
Flickr terms of use for the images",
  "sc:name": "MSCOCO",
  "sc:url": "https://cocodataset.org/",
  "sc:creator": "COCO Consortium: Tsung-Yi Lin, Michael Maire, Serge
Belongie, Lubomir Bourdev, Ross Girshick, James Hays, Pietro Perona, Deva
Ramanan, C. Lawrence Zitnick, Piotr Dollar",
  "sc:publisher": "COCO Consortium: Tsung-Yi Lin, Michael Maire, Serge
Belongie, Lubomir Bourdev, Ross Girshick, James Hays, Pietro Perona, Deva
Ramanan, C. Lawrence Zitnick, Piotr Dollar",
  "sc:datePublished": "2014",
  "sc:inLanguage": "en",
  "cr:citeAs": "https://arxiv.org/abs/1405.0312",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "yes",
// RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "Amazon's Mechanical Turk is used to crowdsource the
annotation of the images",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
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"rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Amazon's Mechanical Turk",
"rai:annotatorDemographics": "Active workers in the Mechanical Turk
marketplace",
"rai:dataUseCases": "Object detection, segmentation, captioning",
"rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "NA"
}
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- Annotator 3:

```
{
// Croissant core attributes
"sc:description": "COCO is a large-scale object detection, segmentation,
and captioning dataset. COCO has several features:
Object segmentation
Recognition in context
Superpixel stuff segmentation
330K images (>200K labeled)
1.5 million object instances
80 object categories
91 stuff categories
5 captions per image
250,000 people with keypoints",
"sc:license": "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License",
"sc:name": "Microsoft COCO",
"sc:url": "https://cocodataset.org/#home",
"sc:creator": "Tsung-Yi Lin Cornell NYC Tech and the Cornell
Computer Science Department,
Michael Maire Toyota Technological Institute at Chicago,
Serge Belongie Cornell NYC Tech and the Cornell
Computer Science Department,
Lubomir Bourdev Facebook AI Research,
Ross Girshick Microsoft Research, Redmond,
James Hays Brown University,
Pietro Perona California Institute of Technology,
Deva Ramanan University of California at Irvine,
C. Lawrence Zitnick Microsoft Research, Redmond,
Piotr Dollar Facebook AI Research",
"sc:publisher": "COCO Consortium",
"sc:datePublished": "May 2014",
"sc:inLanguage": "English",
"cr:citeAs": "@inproceedings{lin2014microsoft,
title={Microsoft coco: Common objects in context},
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```

        author={Lin, Tsung-Yi and Maire, Michael and Belongie, Serge
and Hays, James and Perona, Pietro and Ramanan, Deva and Doll{\`a}r, Piotr and
Zitnick, C Lawrence},
        booktitle={Computer Vision--ECCV 2014: 13th European
Conference, Zurich, Switzerland, September 6-12, 2014, Proceedings, Part V 13},
        pages={740--755},
        year={2014},
        organization={Springer}
    }",
    "cr:isLiveDataset": "False",
    // RAI attributes
    "rai:dataCollection": "To create a large-scale dataset a large set of
images containing contextual relationships and non iconic object views was
harvested. TO achieve this, the technique used queries for pairs of objects in
conjunction with images retrieved via scene-based queries. Next, each image was
labeled as containing particular object categories using a hierarchical
labeling approach. For each category found, the individual instances were
labeled, verified, and finally segmented.",
    "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
    "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Amazon's Mechanical Turk and all the
creators of the dataset",
    "rai:annotatorDemographics": "Creators of this dataset.",
    "rai:dataUseCases": "image segmentation, object detection, classification,
",
    "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "The COCO Consortium does not own the
copyright of the images. Use of the images must abide by the Flickr Terms of
Use. The users of the images accept full responsibility for the use of the
dataset, including but not limited to the use of any copies of copyrighted
images that they may create from the dataset."
}

```

Dataset 8 - MMMU dataset

- **Overview of Dataset 1:**
 - Link: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/MMMU/MMMU>
- **Annotator 1:**

```

{
  // Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "A benchmark designs to evaluate multimodal models on massive multi-discipline task demanding college-level subject knowledge and deliberate reasonin. MMMU includes 11.5K meticulously collected multimodal questions from college exams, quizzes, and textbooks, covering six core disciplines: Art & Design, Business, Science, Health & Medicine, Humanities & Social Science, and Tech & Engineering. These questions span 30 subjects and 183 subfields, comprising 30 highly heterogeneous image types, such as charts, diagrams, maps, tables, music sheets, and chemical structures. Unlike existing benchmarks, MMMU focuses on advanced perception and reasoning with domain-specific knowledge, challenging models to perform tasks akin to those faced by experts",
  "sc:license": "Apache-2.0 license",
  "sc:name": "MMMU",
  "sc:url": "https://mmmu-benchmark.github.io/",
  "sc:creator":
    [
      {
        "@type": "Person",
        "email": "mailto:xiangyue@in.ai",
        "name": "Xiang Yue",
      },
      {
        "@type": "Person",
        "name": "Yuansheng Ni",
      },
      {
        "@type": "Person",
        "name": "Kai Zhang",
      },
      {
        "@type": "Person",
        "email": "mailto:xiangyue@in.ai",
        "name": "Tianyu Zheng",
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  "sc:publisher": "arXiv",
  "sc:datePublished": "12/21/2023",
  "sc:inLanguage": "English",
  "cr:citeAs": " @inproceedings{yue2023mmmu,
    title={MMMU: A Massive Multi-discipline Multimodal Understanding and Reasoning Benchmark for Expert AGI},

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```

        author={Xiang Yue and Yuansheng Ni and Kai Zhang and Tianyu Zheng
and Ruoqi Liu and Ge Zhang and Samuel Stevens and Dongfu Jiang and
Weiming Ren and Yuxuan Sun and Cong Wei and Botao Yu and Ruibin Yuan and
Renliang Sun and Ming Yin and Boyuan Zheng and Zhenzhu Yang and Yibo Liu
and Wenhao Huang and Huan Sun and Yu Su and Wenhui Chen},
        booktitle={Proceedings of CVPR},
        year={2024},
    }
},
    "cr:isLiveDataset": "1",
// RAI attributes
    "rai:dataCollection": "The dataset collection takes three stages. Firstly,
we go through the common university majors to decide what subjects should be
included in our benchmark. The selection is based on the principle that visual
inputs should be commonly adopted in the subjects to provide valuable
information. Through this principle, we rule out a few subjects like law and
linguistics because it is difficult to find enough relevant multimodal problems
in these subjects. Consequently, we select 30 subjects from six different
disciplines.",
    "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
    "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Unknown",
    "rai:annotatorDemographics": "Students",
    "rai:dataUseCases": "Testing LLM advanced perception andreasoning with
domain-specific knowledge, challenging models to perform tasks akin to those
faced by experts",
    "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": ["Compliance with privacy laws and
ethical standards in data handling is paramount. The annotators should avoid
collecting questions that contain any private information., Strict adherence to
copyright and licensing regulations is mandatory. Data from sources that
prohibit copying or redistribution will be explicitly avoided.",
"Strict adherence to copyright and licensing regulations is mandatory. Data
from sources that prohibit copying or redistribution will be explicitly
avoided."]
}

```

- Annotator 2:

```
{
// Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "MMMU is a benchmark for evaluating multimodal models on massive multi-discipline tasks. It requires college-level subject knowledge and deliberate reasoning. MMMU includes 11.5K meticulously collected multimodal questions from college exams, quizzes, and textbooks, covering six core disciplines: Art & Design, Business, Science, Health & Medicine, Humanities & Social Science, and Tech & Engineering. These questions span 30 subjects and 183 subfields, comprising 30 highly heterogeneous image types, such as charts, diagrams, maps, tables, music sheets, and chemical structures. Unlike existing benchmarks, MMMU focuses on advanced perception and reasoning with domain-specific knowledge, challenging models to perform tasks akin to those faced by experts",
  "sc:license": "Apache-2.0",
  "sc:name": "mmmu",
  "sc:url": "https://mmmu-benchmark.github.io/",
  "sc:creator": [{"@type": "Person", "name": "Xiang Yue"},
    {"@type": "Person", "name": "Yuansheng Ni"},
    {"@type": "Person", "name": "Kai Zhang"},
    {"@type": "Person", "name": "Tianyu Zheng"},
    {"@type": "Person", "name": "Ruoqi Liu"},
    {"@type": "Person", "name": "Ge Zhang"},
    {"@type": "Person", "name": "Samuel Stevens"},
    {"@type": "Person", "name": "Dongfu Jiang"},
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    {"@type": "Person", "name": "Yuxuan Sun"},
    {"@type": "Person", "name": "Cong Wei"},
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    {"@type": "Person", "name": "Renliang Sun"},
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        {"@type": "Person", "name": "Yuxuan Sun"},
        {"@type": "Person", "name": "Cong Wei"},
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        {"@type": "Person", "name": "Yibo Liu"},
        {"@type": "Person", "name": "Wenhao Huang"},
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    "sc:inLanguage": "English",
    "cr:citeAs": " @inproceedings{yue2023mmmu,
        title={MMMU: A Massive Multi-discipline Multimodal Understanding
and Reasoning Benchmark for Expert AGI},
        author={Xiang Yue and Yuansheng Ni and Kai Zhang and Tianyu Zheng
and Ruoqi Liu and Ge Zhang and Samuel Stevens and Dongfu Jiang and
Weiming Ren and Yuxuan Sun and Cong Wei and Botao Yu and Ruibin Yuan and
Renliang Sun and Ming Yin and Boyuan Zheng and Zhenzhu Yang and Yibo Liu
and Wenhao Huang and Huan Sun and Yu Su and Wenhu Chen},
        booktitle={Proceedings of CVPR},
        year={2024},
    }
",
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// RAI attributes
    "rai:dataCollection": "The dataset was collected in three stages. Firstly,
they went through the common university majors to decide what subjects should
be included in the benchmark. The selection was based on the principle that
visual inputs should be commonly adopted in the subjects to provide valuable
information. Consequently, they selected 30 subjects from six different
disciplines. In the second stage, they recruited over 50 university students,
including co-authors, specializing in these majors as annotators to assist in
question collection. They collect multimodal questions from major textbooks and
online resources, creating new questions based on their expertise where

```

```
necessary.",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Unknown",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "Students",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "evaluating multimodal models, evaluating models to
reason with domain-specific knowledge",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "Compliance with privacy laws and
ethical standards in data handling is paramount. The annotators should avoid
collecting questions that contain any private information."
}
```

- **Annotator 3:**

```

{
// Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "A benchmark designed to evaluate multimodal models on massive multi-discipline tasks demanding college-level subject knowledge and deliberate reasoning. MMMU includes 11.5K meticulously collected multimodal questions from college exams, quizzes, and textbooks, covering six core disciplines: Art & Design, Business, Science, Health & Medicine, Humanities & Social Science, and Tech & Engineering. These questions span 30 subjects and 183 subfields, comprising 30 highly heterogeneous image types, such as charts, diagrams, maps, tables, music sheets, and chemical structures.",
  "sc:license": "Apache-2.0 license",
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  "sc:url": "https://mmmu-benchmark.github.io/",
  "sc:creator": "Xiang Yue IN.AI Research,
    Yuansheng Ni University of Waterloo, Kai Zhang University of Waterloo,
    Tianyu Zheng The Ohio State University,
    Ruoqi Liu The Ohio State University,
    Ge Zhang Independent,
    Samuel Stevens The Ohio State University,
    Dongfu Jiang University of Waterloo,
    Weiming Ren University of Waterloo,
    Yuxuan Sun Independent,
    Cong Wei University of Waterloo,
    Botao Yu The Ohio State University,
    Ruibin Yuan Carnegie Mellon University,
    Renliang Sun University of Waterloo,,
    Ming Yin Princeton University,
    Boyuan Zheng The Ohio State University,
    Zhenzhu Yang Independent,
    Yibo Liu University of Victoria,
    Wenhao Huang Independent,
    Huan Sun The Ohio State University,
    Yu Su The Ohio State University,
    Wenhao Chen University of Waterloo,",
    "sc:publisher": "https://huggingface.co/datasets/MMMU/MMMU",
    "sc:datePublished": "12/21/2023",
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    "cr:citeAs": "@inproceedings{yue2023mmmu,
      title={MMMU: A Massive Multi-discipline Multimodal Understanding and Reasoning Benchmark for Expert AGI},
      author={Xiang Yue and Yuansheng Ni and Kai Zhang and Tianyu Zheng and Ruoqi Liu and Ge Zhang and Samuel Stevens and Dongfu Jiang and Weiming Ren and Yuxuan Sun and Cong Wei and Botao Yu and Ruibin Yuan and Renliang Sun and Ming Yin and Boyuan Zheng and Zhenzhu Yang and Yibo Liu and

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    Wenhao Huang and Huan Sun and Yu Su and Wenhui Chen},
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// RAI attributes
    "rai:dataCollection": "The dataset collection is based on three stages.
    Firstly, we go through the common university majors to decide what subjects
    should be included in our benchmark. The selection is based on the principle
    that visual inputs should be commonly adopted in the subjects to provide
    valuable information. Through this principle, we rule out a few subjects like
    law and linguistics because it is difficult to find enough relevant multimodal
    problems in these subjects. Consequently, we select 30 subjects from six
    different disciplines. In the second stage, we recruit over 50 university
    students, including co-authors, specializing in these majors as annotators to
    assist in question collection. They collect multimodal questions from major
    textbooks and online resources, creating new questions based on their expertise
    where necessary. The annotators are instructed to adhere to copyright and
    license regulations, avoiding data from sites prohibiting copy and
    redistribution. Given the arising data contamination concerns of foundation
    models, the annotators are advised to select questions without immediately
    available answers, such as those with answers in separate documents or at the
    end of textbooks. This process results in a diverse collection of 13K questions
    from various sources.",
    "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
    "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "University",
    "rai:annotatorDemographics": "University Students and co-authors of the
    dataset",
    "rai:dataUseCases": "MMMU is designed to measure three essential skills in
    LMMs: perception, knowledge, and reasoning. The aim is to evaluate how well
    these models can not only perceive and understand information across different
    modalities but also apply reasoning with subject-specific knowledge to derive
    the solution.",
    "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "The guidelines for the annotators
    emphasized strict compliance with copyright and licensing rules from the
    initial data source, specifically avoiding materials from websites that forbid
    copying and redistribution. Should you encounter any data samples potentially
    breaching the copyright or licensing regulations of any site, we encourage you
    to notify us. Upon verification, such samples will be promptly removed."
}

```

Dataset 9 - Visual Genome dataset

- **Overview of Dataset:**
 - Link: https://huggingface.co/datasets/visual_genome
- **Annotator 1:**

```
{
// Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "The Visual Genome dataset is created with the aim of
training and benchmarking the next generation of computer models for
comprehensive scene understanding. Visual Genome has:
108,077 image
5.4 Million Region Descriptions
1.7 Million Visual Question Answers
3.8 Million Object Instances
2.8 Million Attributes
2.3 Million Relationships",
  "sc:license": "Visual Genome by Ranjay Krishna is licensed under a Creative
Commons Attribution 4.0 International License",
  "sc:name": "Visual Genome dataset",
  "sc:url": "https://doi.org/10.1007/s11263-016-0981-7",
  "sc:creator": "Ranjay Krishna",
  "sc:publisher": "International Journal of Computer Vision",
  "sc:datePublished": "February 06, 2017",
  "sc:inLanguage": "English",
  "cr:citeAs": "@article{Krishna2016VisualGC,
          title={Visual Genome: Connecting Language and Vision Using
Crowdsourced Dense Image Annotations},
          author={Ranjay Krishna and Yuke Zhu and Oliver Groth and
Justin Johnson and Kenji Hata and Joshua Kravitz and Stephanie Chen and Yannis
Kalantidis and Li-Jia Li and David A. Shamma and Michael S. Bernstein and Li
Fei-Fei},
          journal={International Journal of Computer Vision},
          year={2017},
          volume={123},
          pages={32-73},
          url={https://doi.org/10.1007/s11263-016-0981-7},
          doi={10.1007/s11263-016-0981-7}}",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "No",
// RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "The dataset was collected over the course of 6
months after 15 months of experimentation and iteration on the data
representation. Approximately 800, 000 Human Intelligence Tasks (HITs) were
launched on AMT, where each HIT involved creating descriptions, questions and
answers, or region graphs. Each HIT was designed such that workers manage to
earn anywhere between $6-$8 per hour if they work continuously, in line with
```

```

ethical research standards on Mechanical Turk. Visual Genome HITs achieved a
94.1% retention rate, meaning that 94.1% of workers who completed one of our
tasks went ahead to do more. 93.02% of workers contributed from the United
States. The majority of workers were between the ages of 25 and 34 years old.
The youngest contributor was 18 years and the oldest was 68 years old. It was a
near-balanced split of 54.15% male and 45.85% female workers.",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "six months",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Amazon Mechanical Turk (AMT)",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "The majority of workers were between the ages
of 25 and 34 years old. The youngest contributor was 18 years and the oldest
was 68 years old. The data has a near-balanced split of 54.15% male and 45.85%
female workers.",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "Image-to-Text, Object Detection, Visual Question
Answering, attribute classification, relationship classification, description
generation, and question answering, Dense Image Captioning, Image Understanding
, Relationship Extraction, Semantic Image Retrieval, Completing the Set of
Annotations, Visual Question Answering ",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "Unknown"
}

```

- **Annotator 2:**

```

{
// Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "Visual Genome is a dataset, a knowledge base, an ongoing
effort to connect structured image concepts to language. Visual Genome has:

108,077 image
5.4 Million Region Descriptions
1.7 Million Visual Question Answers
3.8 Million Object Instances
2.8 Million Attributes
2.3 Million Relationships
",
  "sc:license": "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License",
  "sc:name": "Visual Genome",
  "sc:url": "https://huggingface.co/datasets/visual_genome",
  "sc:creator": "Ranjay Krishna and Yuke Zhu and Oliver Groth and Justin
Johnson and Kenji Hata and Joshua Kravitz and Stephanie Chen and Yannis
Kalantidis and Li-Jia Li and David A. Shamma and Michael S. Bernstein and Li
Fei-Fei",
  "sc:publisher": "Stanford CS",
  "sc:datePublished": "2017",

```

```

    "sc:inLanguage": "English",
    "cr:citeAs": "@article{Krishna2016VisualGC,
    title={Visual Genome: Connecting Language and Vision Using Crowdsourced Dense
Image Annotations},
    author={Ranjay Krishna and Yuke Zhu and Oliver Groth and Justin Johnson and
Kenji Hata and Joshua Kravitz and Stephanie Chen and Yannis Kalantidis and
Li-Jia Li and David A. Shamma and Michael S. Bernstein and Li Fei-Fei},
    journal={International Journal of Computer Vision},
    year={2017},
    volume={123},
    pages={32-73},
    url={https://doi.org/10.1007/s11263-016-0981-7},
    doi={10.1007/s11263-016-0981-7}
}
",
    "cr:isLiveDataset": "Unknown",
// RAI attributes
    "rai:dataCollection": "Unknown",
    "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
    "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Amazon Mechanical Turk (AMT)",
    "rai:annotatorDemographics": "The majority of our workers were between the
ages of 25 and 34 years old.Our youngest contributor was 18 years old and the
old-est was 68 years old. We also had a near-balanced split of 54.15% male and
45.85% female workers.",
    "rai:dataUseCases": "a general-purpose representation of the visual world,
without bias towards a particular task.",
    "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "false"
}

```

- **Annotator 3:**

```

{
// Croissant core attributes
    "sc:description": "Visual Genome is a dataset, a knowledge base, an ongoing
effort to connect structured image concepts to language.

```

From the paper:

Despite progress in perceptual tasks such as image classification, computers still perform poorly on cognitive tasks such as image description and question answering. Cognition is core to tasks that involve not just recognizing, but reasoning about our visual world.

However, models used to tackle the rich content in images for cognitive tasks are still being trained using the same datasets designed for perceptual tasks. To achieve success at cognitive tasks, models need to understand the interactions and relationships between objects in an image. When asked “What vehicle is the person riding?”, computers will need to identify the objects in an image as well as the relationships riding(man, carriage) and pulling(horse, carriage) to answer correctly that “the person is riding a horse-drawn carriage.”

```
",
  "sc:license": "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0",
  "sc:name": "visual_genome",
  "sc:url": "https://huggingface.co/datasets/visual_genome",
  "sc:creator": "Ranjay Krishna et. al",
  "sc:publisher": "International Journal of Computer Vision",
  "sc:datePublished": "06 February 2017",
  "sc:inLanguage": "English",
  "cr:citeAs": "@article{Krishna2016VisualGC,
    title={Visual Genome: Connecting Language and Vision Using Crowdsourced Dense Image Annotations},
    author={Ranjay Krishna and Yuke Zhu and Oliver Groth and Justin Johnson and Kenji Hata and Joshua Kravitz and Stephanie Chen and Yannis Kalantidis and Li-Jia Li and David A. Shamma and Michael S. Bernstein and Li Fei-Fei},
    journal={International Journal of Computer Vision},
    year={2017},
    volume={123},
    pages={32-73},
    url={https://doi.org/10.1007/s11263-016-0981-7},
    doi={10.1007/s11263-016-0981-7}
  }
",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "",
  // RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "Visual Genome was collected and verified entirely by crowd workers from Amazon Mechanical Turk.",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "The dataset was collected over the course of 6 months after 15 months of experimentation and iteration on the data representation.",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Manual Human Curator",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "The majority of our workers were between the ages of 25 and 34 years old. Our youngest contributor was 18 years old and the oldest was 68 years old. We also had a near-balanced split of 54.15% male and 45.85% female workers. Country Distribution; United States 93.02%, Philippines
```

```

1.29%, Kenya 1.13%, India 0.94%, Russia 0.50%, Canada 0.47%, (Others) 2.65%",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "The Visual Genome dataset is among the first to
provide a detailed labeling of object interactions and attributes, grounding
visual concepts to language; computer vision.",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": ""
}

```

Dataset 10 - MathVista dataset

- **Overview of Dataset:**
 - Link: <https://huggingface.co/datasets/AI4Math/MathVista>
- **Annotator 1:**

```

{
  // Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "MathVista is a consolidated Mathematical reasoning
benchmark within Visual contexts. It consists of three newly created datasets,
IQTest, FunctionQA, and PaperQA, which address the missing visual domains and
are tailored to evaluate logical reasoning on puzzle test figures, algebraic
reasoning over functional plots, and scientific reasoning with academic paper
figures, respectively. It also incorporates 9 MathQA datasets and 19 VQA
datasets from the literature, which significantly enrich the diversity and
complexity of visual perception and mathematical reasoning challenges within
our benchmark. In total, MathVista includes 6,141 examples collected from 31
different datasets.",
  "sc:license": "CC BY-SA 4.0",
  "sc:name": "MathVista",
  "sc:url": "https://mathvista.github.io/",
  "sc:creator": " Pan Lu UCLA, Microsoft Research, Redmond,
Hritik Bansal UCLA,
Tony Xia UCLA,
Jiacheng Liu University of Washington,
Chunyuan Li Microsoft Research, Redmond,
Hannaneh Hajishirzi University of Washington,
Hao Cheng Microsoft Research, Redmond,
Kai-Wei Chang UCLA,
Michel Galley Microsoft Research, Redmond,
Jianfeng Gao Microsoft Research, Redmond,
"],
  "sc:publisher": "ICLR 2024",
  "sc:datePublished": "January 21, 2024",
}

```

```
"sc:inLanguage": "English",
"cr:citeAs": "@inproceedings{lu2024mathvista,
    author = {Lu, Pan and Bansal, Hritik and Xia, Tony and Liu,
    Jiacheng and Li, Chunyuan and Hajishirzi, Hannaneh and Cheng, Hao and Chang,
    Kai-Wei and Galley, Michel and Gao, Jianfeng},
    title = {MathVista: Evaluating Mathematical Reasoning of
    Foundation Models in Visual Contexts},
    booktitle = {International Conference on Learning
    Representations (ICLR)},
    year = {2024}}",
"cr:isLiveDataset": "No",
// RAI attributes
"rai:dataCollection": "Collection of MathQA datasets- We collected nine
MathQA datasets in multimodal settings, including four for GPS, two for MWP
with visual contexts of synthetic scenes, abstract diagrams, and
tables, and two for TQA on college curricula. Annotations such as solutions,
programs, parsing results, and grounded theorems are also collected, providing
demonstration examples for LLMs. Each source dataset is limited to up to 400
examples to ensure a balanced representation of each source in our final
compiled benchmark. In total, we collected 2,666 examples.
Review and collection of VQA datasets- Many existing VQA datasets feature
instances requiring mathematical reasoning abilities, such as arithmetic
operations or numeric common sense. Incorporating these datasets enhances
problem diversity in terms of tasks, domains, visual contexts, and
reasoning skills involved. We reviewed more than 70 datasets, collecting 19 of
them that contain math-related instances and are publicly available. Since
these datasets are not originally math-targeted, we initially designed
heuristic rules to automatically select examples likely
to involve mathematical reasoning from a large pool of candidates. Examples
with numeric answers or those containing quantity words in the questions were
selected. This automatic filtration yielded 4,949 VQA-format examples, though
some false positive examples remained. Therefore, we engaged three expert
annotators to manually label these examples to determine if they involve
mathematical reasoning. Utilizing majority voting and
limiting each source dataset to 400 examples, we finalized a collection of
2,739 examples. Collection of three new datasets. While the source datasets we
collected encompass multiple visual contexts and mathematical reasoning
abilities, certain scenarios remain unaddressed: logical reasoning on puzzle
test diagrams, statistical reasoning on functional plots, and scientific
reasoning on academic figures. To address these gaps, we introduced three new
datasets: IQTest, FunctionQA, and PaperQA, with examples illustrated in Figure
2. IQTest comprises 228 examples requiring inductive reasoning, abstract
thinking, pattern prediction, and calculations, sourced from puzzle test
figures on online learning platforms. FunctionQA, with 400 examples, emphasizes
subtle visual perceptions of functional plots and algebraic reasoning
```

concerning variables, expressions, equations, and functions. PaperQA is a novel dataset featuring questions derived from informative academic illustrations, including tables, figures, and charts from online education resources, with 107 examples sourced from papers released in August 2023 on Huggingface.",

```
"rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",  
"rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Annotation tool developed by the authors",  
"rai:annotatorDemographics": "Graduate students",  
"rai:dataUseCases": "Multiple choice, question answering, visual question answering",  
"rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "The dataset can be used commercially as a test set, but using it as a training set is prohibited. By accessing or using this dataset, you acknowledge and agree to abide by these terms in conjunction with the CC BY-SA 4.0 license."  
}
```

- **Annotator 2:**

```
{  
  // Croissant core attributes  
  "sc:description": "MathVista is a consolidated Mathematical reasoning benchmark within Visual contexts. It consists of three newly created datasets, IQTest, FunctionQA, and PaperQA, which address the missing visual domains and are tailored to evaluate logical reasoning on puzzle test figures, algebraic reasoning over functional plots, and scientific reasoning with academic paper figures, respectively. It also incorporates 9 MathQA datasets and 19 VQA datasets from the literature, which significantly enrich the diversity and complexity of visual perception and mathematical reasoning challenges within our benchmark. In total, MathVista includes 6,141 examples collected from 31 different datasets",  
  "sc:license": "The new contributions to our dataset are distributed under the CC BY-SA 4.0 license, including  
  
The creation of three datasets: IQTest, FunctionQA, and Paper;  
The filtering and cleaning of source datasets;  
The standard formalization of instances for evaluation purposes;  
The annotations of metadata.  
The copyright of the images and the questions belongs to the original authors, and the source of every image and original question can be found in the metadata field and in the source.json file. Alongside this license, the following conditions apply:
```

```
Purpose: The dataset was primarily designed for use as a test set.
```

Commercial Use: The dataset can be used commercially as a test set, but using it as a training set is prohibited. By accessing or using this dataset, you acknowledge and agree to abide by these terms in conjunction with the CC BY-SA 4.0 license.

```
",
  "sc:name": "MathVista",
  "sc:url": "https://huggingface.co/datasets/AI4Math/MathVista",
  "sc:creator": "Lu, Pan and Bansal, Hritik and Xia, Tony and Liu, Jiacheng
and Li, Chunyuan and Hajishirzi, Hannaneh and Cheng, Hao and Chang, Kai-Wei and
Galley, Michel and Gao, Jianfeng",
  "sc:publisher": "UCLA, Microsoft Research",
  "sc:datePublished": "Unknown",
  "sc:inLanguage": "English",
  "cr:citeAs": "@inproceedings{lu2024mathvista,
  author = {Lu, Pan and Bansal, Hritik and Xia, Tony and Liu, Jiacheng and Li,
Chunyuan and Hajishirzi, Hannaneh and Cheng, Hao and Chang, Kai-Wei and Galley,
Michel and Gao, Jianfeng},
  title = {MathVista: Evaluating Mathematical Reasoning of Foundation Models in
Visual Contexts},
  booktitle = {International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)},
  year = {2024}
}
",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "Unknown",
  // RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "We collected nine MathQA datasets in multimodal
settings, including four for GPS, two for MWP with visual contexts of synthetic
scenes, abstract diagrams, and tables, and two for TQA on college curricula
(see §C.4). Annotations such as solutions, programs, parsing results, and
grounded theorems are also collected, providing demonstration examples for
LLMs. Each source dataset is limited to up to 400 examples to ensure a balanced
representation of each source in our final compiled benchmark. In total, we
collected 2,666 examples.",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "Unknown",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "Custom Tool",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "Eligible human annotators must have a
satisfactory annotating history, successfully pass qualification examples, and
possess a high school degree or higher.",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "logical reasoning on puzzle test figures, algebraic
reasoning over functional plots, and scientific reasoning with academic paper
figures",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": "false"
}
```

- Annotator 3:

```
{
// Croissant core attributes
  "sc:description": "MathVista is a consolidated Mathematical reasoning benchmark within Visual contexts. It consists of three newly created datasets, IQTest, FunctionQA, and PaperQA, which address the missing visual domains and are tailored to evaluate logical reasoning on puzzle test figures, algebraic reasoning over functional plots, and scientific reasoning with academic paper figures, respectively. It also incorporates 9 MathQA datasets and 19 VQA datasets from the literature, which significantly enrich the diversity and complexity of visual perception and mathematical reasoning challenges within our benchmark. In total, MathVista includes 6,141 examples collected from 31 different datasets.",
  "sc:license": "cc-by-sa-4.0",
  "sc:name": "MathVista",
  "sc:url":
"https://huggingface.co/datasets/AI4Math/MathVista/blob/main/README.md#dataset-description",
  "sc:creator": "Pan Lu",
  "sc:publisher": "ICLR 2024/ArXiv",
  "sc:datePublished": "21 Jan 2024",
  "sc:inLanguage": "English, Chinese, Persian",
  "cr:citeAs": "@inproceedings{lu2024mathvista,
  author = {Lu, Pan and Bansal, Hritik and Xia, Tony and Liu, Jiacheng and Li, Chunyuan and Hajishirzi, Hannaneh and Cheng, Hao and Chang, Kai-Wei and Galley, Michel and Gao, Jianfeng},
  title = {MathVista: Evaluating Mathematical Reasoning of Foundation Models in Visual Contexts},
  booktitle = {International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)},
  year = {2024}
}",
  "cr:isLiveDataset": "No",
// RAI attributes
  "rai:dataCollection": "The MathVISTA dataset comprises nine MathQA datasets in multimodal settings, including GPS, MWP, and TQA, with annotations such as solutions and parsing results, totaling 2,666 examples; additionally, 19 VQA datasets containing math-related instances were reviewed, resulting in 2,739 examples after heuristic selection and manual labeling; three new datasets addressing unaddressed scenarios were introduced: IQTest, FunctionQA, and PaperQA, totaling 735 examples, annotated by graduate students in STEM fields; metadata annotation facilitates comprehensive analysis of models' reasoning capabilities across various aspects, with automatic annotation achieving high accuracy; finally, MathVISTA consists of 6,141 examples divided into testmini
```

```
and test subsets, with rigorous quality checks ensuring dataset integrity.",
  "rai:dataCollectionTimeframe": "The study comprised five test questions and
two qualification questions, which were to be answered within a 20-minute
timeframe.",
  "rai:dataAnnotationPlatform": "The annotations were conducted using Amazon
Mechanical Turk, where eligible human annotators had to meet specific criteria
and complete a qualification process, involving a satisfactory history, passing
qualification examples, and possessing at least a high school degree; each
annotator was tasked with completing five questions within a 20-minute time
frame.",
  "rai:annotatorDemographics": "STEM graduate students",
  "rai:dataUseCases": "benchmark for testing the mathematical ability of
models",
  "rai:personalSensitiveInformation": ""
}
```

Annotator Demographics Information

It is important to note the annotator background for understanding the biases in the evaluation process. Below is some statistical information about the annotator demographics.

Age Range

Age group
9 responses

Gender

Gender
9 responses

Educational Background

Education
9 responses

First Language

Is English your first language?

9 responses

Summary of the Evaluation Details

1. Confidence

How confident are you that your provided annotations are correct?

32 responses

The above figure shows the participants' confidence in the annotations they provided, on a scale of 1 to 5. The majority of participants picked 4, which shows a high level of confidence in their ability to create Croissant metadata.

2. Understanding of the dataset

How well did you understand the dataset (e.g. the task, domain, modality, etc.)?

1 2 3 4 5

I don't understand the dataset at all the dataset (incl. its purpose, creation, etc.) is very clear and understandable for me

32 responses

It's interesting to contrast this number with the participants' level of understanding of datasets which varies more broadly between 3 and 5.

3. Time noted to complete the evaluation

How long did it take to annotate the dataset with the requested Croissant attributes?

- Up to 15 minutes
- between 15-30 minutes
- more than 30 minutes

32 responses

Fig. 2 gives an overview of how much time participants took for the user study. The majority of participants took 15-30 minutes to create the Croissant description of a dataset, which seems like a reasonable amount of time.

4. Consistency

Is there any (in your opinion important) information about the dataset which you can't define using Croissant?

Please check the Croissant specification

(<https://mlcommons.github.io/croissant/docs/croissant-spec.html>) for more details on Croissant attributes.

1 2 3 4 5

yes, there is lots of critical information about the dataset, Croissant does not capture no, every important information about this dataset, which might be useful for ML users, is capture in Croissant attributes

32 responses

5. Conciseness

Did you find any of the Croissant attributes which we asked you to annotate, redundant and not definable for this dataset?

1 2 3 4 5

yes, there are lots of redundant attributes no, none of the attributes is redundant

32 responses

6. Readability

How intuitive are the Croissant attributes names for you? E.g. An attribute's name is not intuitive if you needed to check the specification website to understand what the attribute name means?

32 responses

7. Understanding of the Specification

Rate the ease of understanding the Croissant specification.

1 2 3 4 5

it was very hard to understand the specification the specification is very easy to understand

32 responses

Future Directions:

This preliminary report consists of details for the manual evaluation of the Croissant files. In future, the Working Group intends to make the evaluation process more smooth and efficient so that the sample set of participants can be increased.

References

- Al Kuwatly, H., Wich, M., & Groh, G. (2020, November). Identifying and measuring annotator bias based on annotators' demographic characteristics. In *Proceedings of the fourth workshop on online abuse and harms* (pp. 184-190).
- Pei, J., & Jurgens, D. (2023). When do annotator demographics matter? measuring the influence of annotator demographics with the popquorn dataset. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.06826*.
- <https://github.com/mawic/annotator-bias-demographic-characteristics>

Acknowledgments

We thank the annotators and other contributors for being a part of this user research.